

ISSUE 2
2022

AFTER CONSTANTINE
STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND
EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

AFTER CONSTANTINE

STORIES FROM
THE LATE
ANTIQUÉ AND
EARLY
BYZANTINE
ERA

ORTHODOX ACADEMY OF CRETE

AFTER CONSTANTINE

STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND
EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

ISSN 2732-8260

After Constantine issue 2 (June 2022)

Published by the Orthodox Academy of Crete (www.oac.gr)

All papers copyright are held by the authors and became available by the Creative Commons Attribution License

CC-BY creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0

EDITORIAL BOARD

Andreas Kuelzer, Professor of Byzantine studies,
Austrian Academy of Sciences

Panagiotis Manafis, Research Fellow at the Institute for
Textual Scholarship and Electronic Editing, University
of Birmingham, Adjunct Lecturer of Byzantine
Philology, University of Patras

Zoe Tsiami, PhD Candidate in Late Antique History,
University of Thessaly

Sercan Yandim Aydin, Associate Professor, Dr.
Byzantine art and culture, Hacettepe University

Luca Zavagno, Assistant Professor of Byzantine History,
Bilkent University

Dr Constantine Zorbas, Director of Orthodox Academy
of Crete

TABLE OF CONTENTS

COPTIC OSTRACA MENTIONING

MONEY

SOHAIR AHMED

p. 1

TEACHING GEOGRAPHY.

A NEVER-ENDING DIALOGUE BETWEEN LATE ANTIQUE
AND RENAISSANCE EUROPE

DAVID SALOMONI

p. 23

MEMORY, SOCIETY AND ART AT THE CHURCH OF
SAINT SOPHIA, MYTIKAS, AKARNANIA. THE FUNERARY
CHAMBERS AND THE TOMB IN THE NORTH AISLE

YANNIS VARALIS, GEORGIA KOLETIOU, GOULIELMOS ORESTIDIS

p. 35

AFTER CONSTANTINE

STORIES FROM THE LATE ANTIQUE AND
EARLY BYZANTINE ERA

MEMORY, SOCIETY AND ART IN THE CHURCH AT SAINT SOPHIA, MYTIKAS, AKARNANIA

THE FUNERARY CHAMBERS AND THE TOMB IN THE NORTH AISLE

YANNIS VARALIS, GEORGIA KOLETIOU, GOULIELMOS ORESTIDIS¹

Abstract

The church at Saint Sophia, Mytikas (anc. Alyzia), is a three-aisled basilica dated to the later part of the fifth or the early sixth century. Excavated in the '70s and '80s of the previous century, the church is not yet published. This study focuses on the funerary use of the annexes flanking the north side and on the monumental tomb erected in the north aisle. The character of the burial chambers and the tomb are revealing the collective memory of the late antique community of Alyzians who wanted to preserve both the family ties and the spiritual ties with the deceased. Art, and especially architecture, sculpture, and poetry are the means for organizing and unifying the two sides of a wall.

¹ Yannis D. Varalis is an Associate professor in byzantine archaeology at the University of Thessaly. Georgia Koletiou is a PhD candidate in Byzantine Archaeology at the University of Thessaly. Goulielmos Orestidis is a PhD candidate at the National Technical University.

Keywords: Epirus Vetus, basilica at Saint Sophia, Mytikas, funerary annexes, tomb, collective memory, late antiquity, art.

This study stems from a research project titled: “Memory and Art to the Limit: Church and Society in Byzantine Aetolia and Akarnania” which is carried out under the call “*Development of Human Resources, Education and Lifelong Learning (code: EDBM103) - Support for Researchers with an Emphasis on Young Researchers – Cycle B*” of the Operational Programme “*Development of Human Dynamics, Education and Lifelong Learning*”, which was run from March 2020 to September 2022 and co-financed by Greece and the European Union.

The focus of this project was the study of a late antique church unearthed at the locality of Hagia Sophia, which is situated at 2 km to the east of present-day Mytikas, a seaside village on the west coast of Akarnania. Mytikas is located on a pointed ledge of land into the Ionian Sea and its western bay has been identified with the ancient port of Alyzia, which was known as the “sacred port of Hercules” during the classical period.² The excavation of

² We would like to thank the administrative personnel of the University of Thessaly and all our colleagues of the Ephorate of Antiquities of Aetolia and Akarnania, especially the Ephor Dr. Olympia Vikatou, and the art conservator

the basilica was carried out by Professor Panayotis Vocotopoulos, Member of the Academy of Athens, and his collaborators under the auspices of the Archaeological Society at Athens from 1972 to 1984; between 1973 and 1978 no excavation took place.³

The church is a three-aisled basilica with a semicircular apse to the east and a narthex to the west (**figs. 1-2**). There are no indications that the church had a porticoed atrium or a court. Two annexes are abutting the north wall; the west one was used as a funerary chamber with four graves, one of which contained a marble sarcophagus. In the north aisle, a monumental tomb was erected against the north wall; it consisted of marble pier-colonnettes and slabs with crosses in relief and originally was put under a canopy. The covering marble slab bore an inscribed epitaph assigning the tomb to a distinguished member of the local

Afroditi Tyligada, for their kindness, generosity, and help. In the following footnotes, we use the abbreviations of the Deutsches Archäologisches Institut. For the history and topography of ancient Alyzia, see Katopodis 2000, pp. 66-68; Liagos 2002; Moschos, Portelanos 2010. Cf. also Murray 1982, pp. 82-133 and *passim*. Gehrke, Wirbelauer 2004.

³ Vocotopoulos 1968; 1972; 1979; 1980; 1981; 1982; 1983; 1984. Cf. also Soustal, Koder 1981, p. 170, s.v. “Kandeles”.

Fig. 1. — Mytikas, Saint Sophia, basilica, plan (source: G. Orestidis)

Fig. 2. — Mytikas, Saint Sophia, basilica, longitudinal section
(source: G. Orestidis)

Christian community, possibly named Eunoia or Eurynoa. In this study, we shall focus on the relationship between the tombs in the funerary annex and the monumental tomb in the church.

The annexes of the church

The annexes were excavated in 1980 and a brief description was given by the excavator.⁴ In plan they appear to be three, but there are only two rooms, one to the west, 8.38 m long and 5.16 m wide, and one to the east, 7.07 m long and 5.15 m wide, which is divided into two unequal spaces with a demising wall. Both annexes were designed and built at the same time as the church: the east wall of the church is of an unhindered masonry up to the NE corner of the east room, there are no visible or perceivable construction joints between the interior walls of the annexes and the north wall of the church, and the west wall of the west annex bonds well with the north wall of the church.

The east annex. – The excavation has not provided any evidence that confirms the function of the east annex. It was either empty from the beginning or all of its equipment had been removed before it was left to fall into disrepair. So, its function is inevitably much speculated, because the facts about this room are very few. Firstly, there is a door, 0.80 m wide, leading from the north aisle to the larger space; the floor of this part was paved, possibly from the outset, with clay slabs (diam. 0.31 × 0.26 m) and

⁴ Vocotopoulos 1980, pp. 34-35, pls. 42-45.

wastes of marble plaques, some of which have been brought from somewhere else, since they preserve polished parts, grooves and notches. Secondly, the smaller space (dim. 1.15 × 5.20 m) is separated by the demising wall, 0.50 m thick, into which is opened a low crude door, 0.78 m wide, with a massive hewn stone as a lintel. This space was paved with compact soil and covered by a barrel vault, as is indicated by the traces of the springing of such a vault on the south wall (**fig. 3**). It appears possible that above the lintel of the low door, at a level higher than the surviving walls, there would have been some kind of a flat surface like a shelf, dividing the space into two compartments, one on top of the other. The upper compartment would have been suitable for storing and keeping things or supplies safe and arranged, like a modern reach-in closet or a cupboard with hinged doors. However, this small space did not seem to be visible from the outside and would not have any window for lighting and/or ventilation. We can imagine that it had the form of a closet, where possibly sacred relics or other materials for the funerals or the memorial ceremonies for the deceased were kept. The only finds that have been unearthed inside this small space are fragments of mortar bearing imprints of reeds, which conceivably belonged to the bed layer of the pitched roof of the annex. Professor J.-P. Sodini suggested that the annex could have served the liturgy,

because of the door leading to the north aisle,⁵ which is a conceivable proposition, but it cannot be confirmed.

Fig. 3. — Mytikas, northeast annex, springing of the barrel vault of the west part (source: P.L. Vocotopoulos – no. αςζ'4)

Fig. 4. — Mytikas, northwest (funerary) annex, view from the southwest (source: P.L. Vocotopoulos – no. ας'30)

⁵ Sodini, Kolokotsas 1984, pp. 320-321.

The west annex. – It was undoubtedly a funerary chamber (dim. 8.40 × 5.20 m), since it contains four graves dug into the compact soil (**fig. 4**). The southeast corner surrounds a cist grave made of bricks and mortar: it encloses a marble sarcophagus, 2.05 m long, 0.60 m wide, and 0.35 m deep in the interior. The lid has crosses in low relief in the centers of the sloping sides and acroteria at the corners.⁶ The lid had once been broken at its west end and the missing part was covered hurriedly with two fragments of slabs, which are decorated with Latin crosses in relief with flaring ends. At the northeast corner of the annex, two cist graves are made of vertical stone slabs and covered with ancient hewn blocs. The southwest corner encloses a vaulted tomb (dim. 2.70 × 1.40 m) which has an entrance from the east side, 0.55 m wide. The sides are built of slabs without grout and the barrel vault is made of bricks and mortar. Fragments of glass vessels, lamps and cups or goblets, window panes, and iron nails from the roof timbers, as well as a few pottery sherds, were collected from the layer that covered the graves. No objects accompanying the deceased were found inside the tombs. The bricks and tiles within the upper layers were found blackened by fire, which may indicate the reason the rooms were destroyed and left to fall in ruins.

⁶ Vocotopoulos 1980, p. 35, pl. 44b. Cf. also Papadopoulou 2013, pp. 505–506 no. 129, figs. 129α–γ.

South annex (?). –Two pairs of cobblestones project from the south facade of the church up to 0.10 m from the surface of the wall. These stones indicate that at least another annex, possibly equal in length to the west chamber of the north side, had been planned to be built on the south side, but eventually it did not.⁷ We do not know if this south annex had been planned to be as wide as the north one, but it could have been completely symmetrical. A burial use for this annex is purely hypothetical. Ultimately, the southern porch of the church was probably removed and surrounded by walls, the foundations of which have been revealed around it.⁸

Similar aligned annexes abutting the north wall of a church are not commonly encountered in the sacred architecture of Eastern Illyricum.⁹ Closely related to the Mytikas basilica are three churches in the province of Achaia, one in Thessaly, and three in Macedonia, the vast majority of which lies *extra muros* at a more or less close distance from the city walls. Firstly, in Achaia, twelve annexes in a row are constructed on the north side of the basilica at Kraneion, to the east of the Kenchrean Gate of late antique Corinth; the three eastern most rooms, which are contemporary or slightly postdating the church, are funerary chambers with cist and

⁷ Vocotopoulos 1981, pp. 80–81.

⁸ *Ibid.*, and fig. 1, pl. 77b.

⁹ Cf. Mailis 2011, p. 142.

barrel vaulted graves dug in the soil.¹⁰ Three annexes are abutting the north façade of the basilica at Alike, to the northeast of late antique Argos:¹¹ the median annex, like the east one of the Mytikas basilica, is divided into two compartments, a narrow to the west and a large to the east, and communicates with the north aisle, as well. The excavator identified the purpose of the narrow space as the base of a staircase to the galleries, which is a least convincing hypothesis.¹² A series of four rooms was built on the north side of the basilica at Pikermi, Attica, in the vicinity of a rural late antique settlement:¹³ possibly contemporary with the *quadratum populi*, the rooms are not excavated thoroughly; therefore their utility is highly conjectural.¹⁴ The basilica Delta at Nea Anchialos, near Volos, Thessaly, is thought to be a cemetery church of the late antique city of Phthiotic Thebes: two symmetrical and fairly identical chambers project on either side of the aisles and other two annexes flank the apse, projecting from the east wall. Vaulted tombs have been explored under the mosaic floor of the annex of the south aisle and under the marble floor of the north annex of the

¹⁰ Pallas 1977, pp. 154-156, fig. 107; Mailis 2011, pp. 91-92, no. Ach.23; Leriou, Monolessou 2018, pp. 761-762; Marano 2021, p. 349.

¹¹ Pallas 1977, pp. 177-178, fig. 120.

¹² Mailis 2011, p. 97 no. Ach.32.

¹³ Lazarides 1965, p. 138, plans 5-6.

¹⁴ Mailis 2011, p. 85 no. Ach.9.

apse. Three other annexes have been added in a subsequent period to the north façade of the church, but only one vaulted tomb has been explored in the easternmost room.¹⁵ The basilica of Saint Demetrios at Thessaloniki was a revered healing and pilgrimage center of Eastern Illyricum;¹⁶ on the north façade of the five-aisled basilica, during the second major construction phase of the church, apart from the tomb of the martyr in the north west annex, another small annex with two cist tombs under its floor was explored.¹⁷ To the east of late antique Thessaloniki, the basilica at Toumba district is a church with two annexes on the north side; apart from the tombs explored to the east of the apse, other graves are shown in the north annexes in the published plan of the excavation.¹⁸ Last but not least, the *extra muros* basilica at Philippi, to the east of the late antique city, is a cemetery church, since cist and vaulted tombs have been uncovered under the floors of the nave and aisles, as well as in the annexes. Three rooms in a row are attached to the western part of the north wall of the church: the west room is accessible from the narthex, while the two others are accessible

¹⁵ Pallas 1977, pp. 52-54, fig. 31; Mailis 2011, pp. 76-77, no. Th.11; Marano 2021, pp. 346-347.

¹⁶ Bakirtzis 1997, 507-510 and 2002.

¹⁷ Sorerious 1952, p. 135, pl. 36α, γ; Mailis 2011, pp. 47-48, no. Mac.15. To the north of this chamber, the chapel of Saint John the Baptist and the halls further north received also burials of later dates. Cf. Moutsopoulos 1993-1996 (2003).

¹⁸ Soteriou 1929, 177-178, fig. 9; Mailis 2011, p. 50 no. Mac.18.

from the narthex and the north aisle. Three cist graves have been explored in the two west annexes,¹⁹ and two inscribed tombstones show the importance of the officials of the fourth or fifth century that had been buried there: the tomb in the west annex was that of Mauricius, *vir clarissimus* and *ex-comes*, and the west tomb of the median annex was that of a certain assistant of a comes (*kometianos*).²⁰ The well-known episode from the *Vita* of Saint Thecla, according to which an *officialis* managed to get permission from the local bishop to be buried in the south aisle of the *extra muros* pilgrimage church, but the saint miraculously rebuffed the burial, shows how much local bishops were pressured by aristocrats who wanted to be buried near the holy place of the tomb of a saint.²¹

The funerary chambers of the above-mentioned churches are all rectangular in plan and only two of them, both in Thessaloniki (at Saint Demetrios and the Toumba basilicas), are provided with an apse, which is oriented like the main apse.²² All

¹⁹ Pelekanides 1955, p. 161, fig. 2; Mailis pp. 56–57 no. Mac.33.

²⁰ Cf. Feissel 1983, nos. 251 and 240, respectively; Sodini 1986, p. 234; Marano 2021, p. 341. I was not able to consult the new catalogue of the inscriptions of Philippi by Pilhofer 2009.

²¹ Cf. Dagron 1978, pp. 370–371; Sodini 1986, p. 233; Marano 2021, pp. 353–354.

²² At Saint Demetrios, Thessaloniki, burials multiplied overtime on the north side of the church, for a main street of the city was located along the south

spaces are aligned along the north façade, but in some cases (like the Kraneion basilica and the *extra muros* basilica at Philippi), rooms are also erected along the south and/or the east walls. As we can imagine, each funerary chamber contains tombs, the owners of which are linked by common beliefs, professional companionship and/or blood ties, and from the fourth century onwards funerals are usually undertaken by the family of the dead,²³ therefore, we can assume that the bonds between the living that arranged the burials and the deceased are mostly familial. Thus, the funerary chamber on the north side of the Mytikas basilica presumably belonged to an upper class family of the local Christian community of Alyzians who wanted on the one hand to ensure family bonds between the living and the dead ancestors, and on the other to display these bonds in the public realm by means of the construction of a distinct *cubiculum* or mausoleum, adjacent to the cemetery church of their homeland.

façade and because the church was founded atop the *locus sanctus* of the saint's tomb. Cf. Soterious 1952, pp. 136-137; Mentzos 1994, pp. 43-50; Bakirtzis 1997, 354-356. For the *ad sanctos* burials, cf. Grabar 1946 (1972), pp. 487 ff., spec. 488-493 and, certainly, Duval 1988.

²³ Cf. Rebillard 2003, pp. 148-197; Paxton 2005; Yasin 2005 and 2009, pp. 45-61, with further bibliography.

The monumental tomb

The monumental tomb consists of marble pier-colonnettes and slabs standing on a stylobate that is 3.40 m long and 1.65 m wide

Fig. 5. — Mytikas, north aisle, the monumental tomb after restoration, view from the south (source: Y.D. Varalis)

(**figs. 2 and 5**). Fragments of piers and slabs were found in various parts of the church during the excavation, but today they are put in their initial positions and the missing parts are filled with pinkish cement.²⁴ The stylobate is 0.30 m high and has a classicizing convex and concave profile in its front face; all the other faces are crudely carved. The stylobate possibly comes from an older construction and, in order to be reused here, it has been cut into pieces which were combined to form its current state. The piers-

²⁴ The restoration of the tomb was done by late Yannis Tsevlíkos, under the supervision of Prof. George Velenis. Cf. Vocotopoulos 1984, p. 130.

colonnets (average h. 0.92 m, w. 0.22-0.23 m) are decorated with frames containing a vertical band with forked ends. The slabs (average dim. 1.00 × 0.90 m) are adorned with Latin crosses with expanding ends (average dim. 0.54 × 0.44 m); only the east slab of the south side of the tomb (dim. 1.48 m × 0.92 m) is decorated with two Latin crosses of smaller dimensions (0.435 × 0.38 m). The southeast pier-colonnette preserves on its top surface the base of a colonnette sculpted in the same piece of marble. Thus, the tomb in its original state was placed under a canopy. The stylobate is mounted above the slate stones of the floor of the aisle; the tomb proper was a pit grave, of the covering of which only an ancient hewn bloc has been found *in situ*.

The monumental tomb belonged to a person of high social status in the local Christian community.²⁵ An eight-line epitaph has been carved on a marble slab that formed the lid of the tomb:²⁶

†

[- - - - - εὐσεβ]ίην τε σα<ο>φροσύ-
[νην - - - - -]υρήδισ ἧ τε πόθους

²⁵ Cf. the reconstruction in Vocotopoulos 1983, pp. 84–86, figs 1–4 (plans by G. Velenis).

²⁶ The inscribed slab was found in the debris that covered the north door of the narthex. For the inscription, cf. Vocotopoulos 1972, pp. 112–113, pl. 90b and *SEG* 30, 514.

[- - - - -] α πιστὰ κλέει δήπ[οτε]
 4 [- - - - -] δος ἔτεα πάντα
 [- - - - -] νη πολυήρατον ἄν[δρα]
 [- - - - -] υνόα δίην βιοτήν [- - - -]
 [- - - - -] καὶ θαλάμους ἔλιπ[εν - - -]
 8 [- - - - π]ροσώπου.

†

The lack of typical adjectives that accompany the names of bishops, priests and other clerics, in contrast to other epigrams in dactylic hexameters dedicated to high rank persons from other provinces, like Macedonia, Achaia or Crete,²⁷ suggest that the tomb was not intended for a member of the clergy. The only verb preserved, even partly, is the ἔλιπεν in v. 7; thus, the deceased is probably the grammatical subject of the verbs of the poem and the rest are predicates and clauses. The epigram begins with the virtues of the deceased (εὐσεβίην, σαοφροσύνην, piety, wisdom, v. 1-2) and instances of life (πόθους, κλέει; desires, glory, v. 2-3) and time (δήποτε, πάντα ἔτεα; once, all years, v. 3-4). Although πολυήρατος (v. 5) could be a personal name,²⁸ the use of this word

²⁷ For sepulchral plaques inscribed with epigrams, cf. Bandy 1970, nos. 80, 93, 100, 103 (Crete); Feissel 1985, nos. 20, 36, 51*, 80*, 91*-94* (Peloponnese); Feissel 1983, nos. 5, 6, 60, 61, 202, 230, 265 (Macedonia).

²⁸ Cf. for example, *Polyeratos* in *IG V,2* 323B,45 and 439 from Arkadia, and

in the accusative case specifies that it refers to the person to whom the action of love goes, i.e. a husband or father. The phrase *θαλάμους ἔλιπεν* (v. 7) cannot refer to a man, since *θάλαμος* is the bridal chamber that has been abandoned by the deceased wife. That is why the phrase *δίην βιοτήν* (v. 6) means the excellent, respectful or pious life that the deceased had with her spouse. If this is the case, then we need to find a word in the nominative, which would be most suitable as the grammatical subject, i.e. the person for whom the epigram was made. The only extant part of word that can fit this reasoning is *-υνόα*, which apart from being at the nominative or accusative of the plural of the neutral grammatical gender corresponds also to the nominative of the singular of the feminine gender. And there are feminine personal names ending in *-υνόα*, like *Εὐνόα*²⁹ or *Εὐρυνόα*.³⁰ But this last part of our restitution is a pure hypothesis that cannot be proved.

Hence, the inscription can be transcribed and translated as follows:

Rizakis 2008, no. 116, from Aigion, as well as *IG* XII, 9 191 and 245 from Eretria, Euboea.

²⁹ Cf. *IG* II² 7681 from Attica and *IG* XII,4 2, 653 from Kos(?).

³⁰ Cf., for instance, *IG* IX,1² 2:419 from Akarnania, *SEG* 38, 476 from Bouthrotos, and *SEG* 35, 664 from Krannon, Thessaly. For the Homeric dialect of the inscription, we have consulted Pantazides 1892 and Cunliffe2012.

†

[- - - - - εὐσεβ]ίην τε σα<ο>φροσύ-
 [νην - - - - -]υρήδης ἢ τε πόθους
 [- - - - -]α πιστὰ κλέει δήπ[οτε]
 4 [- - - - -]δος ἔτεα πάντα
 [- - - - -]νη πολυήρατον ἄν[δρα]
 [- - - - - Ε]ὐνόα vel Εὐρ]υνόα δίην βιοτήν [- - - - -]
 [- - - - -] καὶ θαλάμους ἔλιπ[εν - - -]
 8 [- - - - π]ροσώπου.

†

[...] (*Having the virtues of*) piety and wisdom [...] and desires
 [...] with faithfulness once gloriously [...] all years [...] (*with her*)
 endearing man [...]. Eunoa or Eurynoa (*lived*) an excellent life
 [...] and left the bridal rooms [...] her (?) face.

Structures with an arrangement similar to a chancel, with
 slabs between marble pier-colonnettes set on stylobates, are found
 in the south compartment of the transept of the basilicas Beta and
 Delta at Nikopolis,³¹ dated to the last quarter of the fifth century.
 They were undeniably later additions, since they are set directly on
 the floor of the transept area, but their use is debated: Anastasios
 Orlandos and Demetrios Pallas proposed that the structure at the

³¹ Cf. Varalis 2007, pp. 597-598.

basilica Delta was a *pastophorion*, i.e. a secondary table for the deposition of the offerings for the liturgy.³² A similar tomb-like structure affixed to the east wall of the south compartment of the transept at the basilica Beta has passed completely unmentioned by earlier research.³³ The funerary character of the *pastophorion* of basilica Delta has been confirmed,³⁴ but evidence is still needed for the similar structure at the basilica Beta.

A long tradition of funerary receptacles of all kinds, set along the long walls of Early Christian and Byzantine churches, is attested on both the shores of the Adriatic and the Ionian Sea, for instance at the basilica of Sant' Apollinare in Classe,³⁵ and at the basilica of Saint Achilleios on the homonymous island of the Small Prespa Lake.³⁶ As for the crosses with flaring ends in low relief on

³² Orlandos 1959, p. 92. Pallas 1971, coll. 222, 226. Professor J.-P. Sodini makes a list of the *pastophoria* and calls for prudence when trying to interpret their uses (Sodini, Kolokotsas 1984, pp. 123-128, spec. pp. 127-128).

³³ This structure is drawn – although not entirely accurately – on the recently published plan of the church in Zachos 2015, on p. 185.

³⁴ Chalkia 2007, pp. 663-664, plans 1 and 4, figs. 16-17. The cist grave found under the *pastophorion* was constructed with bricks and mortar and the interior was plastered; it contained the relics of at least fifteen deceased.

³⁵ For the church of Sant' Apollinare in Classe, see Mauskopf Deliyannis 2017, pp. 259-274. For the sarcophagi kept at the churches of Ravenna, see Kollwitz, Herdejürgen 1979.

³⁶ See most recently, Moutsopoulos 1999, pp. 135-184.

the slabs at the Mytikas' memorial, sufficient similarities can be found with slabs from the Nikopolis basilicas Beta and Delta,³⁷ but it is not known if any of these slabs originally belonged to a memorial structure in the Nikopolis churches. Slabs decorated with similar Latin crosses have been found in cemetery contexts, like the cover plaque of the tomb no. 3 at the graveyard explored at 74, Nikita Str., Patras,³⁸ or like the one found in the cemetery basilica at Dion, which has been used as an offerings' table for the tomb found nearby, which was dedicated to an unknown saint (or martyr?) named Magna.³⁹ Thus the monumental tomb in the north aisle of the Mytikas basilica is a memorial, a "privileged" tomb,⁴⁰ similar to the tomb-like structures in the basilicas Beta and Delta of Nikopolis, and was built so that the congregation of the Alyzians would offer devotion and reverence when gathered in the

³⁷ Cf. slabs from basilicas Delta (Papadopoulou 2013, pp. 458-459 no. 93; Chalkia 2007, p. 660, fig. 4 and 2015, p. 54), and Beta (Papadopoulou 2013, pp. 471-473, 475, nos 102-104, 106, with the previous bibliography).

³⁸ Koumoussi-Vyenopoulou 1996-1998, pp. 53-54, figs. 4, 5γ; Bozinis 2008, p. 55, no. 3.

³⁹ Mentzos 1990, p. 234, figs. 7-8. Pantermalis 1999, figs. on pp. 260-261; Chalkia 1991, pp. 84-85, figs. 69-70; Marano 2021, pp. 342-343.

⁴⁰ For the 'privileged' tombs, cf. the proceedings of the conferences: Duval, Picard 1986 and De Vingo, Marano, Pinar Gil 2021, and spec. Sodini 1986; Marano 2021.

cemetery church to this pious woman who was hypothetically named Eunoa or Eurynoa.

Society, memory and art

Two interesting facts in the basilica of Mytikas merit our attention. The first is that the northwest annex contains a cist grave with a marble sarcophagus, which is quite uncommon for the province of Epirus Vetus at the end of the fifth or the early sixth century.⁴¹ The second is that this specific tomb with the marble sarcophagus (fig. 6) is located just behind the monumental tomb of the northern aisle of the basilica.

There is only one sarcophagus made of marble that has been brought to light in the province of Epirus Vetus and dated to the late fifth or early sixth century: the sarcophagus found in the northwest angle of the north compartment of the transept at the basilica Delta in Nikopolis, which is made of Proconnesian marble.⁴² The long sides are decorated with crosses with flaring ends that flank a laurel wreath encircling a Christogram; the short

⁴¹ We do not focus here on any possible reuse of the Roman sarcophagi that have been uncovered in Nikopolis. For these sarcophagi, cf. Papaggeli 1984.

⁴² Chalkia 2004; 2007, pp. 660–661, plan3, figs. 7–9; 2015, 56–64, figs. on pp. 57–60. Cf. also Papadopoulou 2013, pp. 503–505 no. 128, figs. 128α–στ. Marano (2021, pp. 343–345 and n. 60) mentions that Constantinopolitan sarcophagi are rarely found outside the capital. The sarcophagus from Ithaca Island is of local stone and probably a local product (cf. Papadopoulou 2013, pp. 506–508 no. 130, figs. 130α–γ).

sides have only one cross each, while the lid has identical crosses upon discs, one at the center of each slope. The similarities between the Nikopolis and the Mytikas sarcophagi are striking: the shape, the carving technique, the material and the execution are

Fig. 6. — Mytikas, northwest annex, tomb with a sarcophagus
(source: P.L. Vocotopoulos – no. ασγ'5)

Fig. 7. — Mytikas, north aisle, the monumental tomb before restoration, view from the east (source: P.L. Vocotopoulos – no. αυια'7)

very close.⁴³ The Mytikas sarcophagus looks today as if of inferior quality, but we should take under account that it has been exposed to air and rain for many years, so the surface of the marble lid shows greater erosion and decay. Thus, both these sarcophagi are possibly products of a Constantinopolitan workshop active around *ca.* 500; we do not know if the Mytikas sarcophagus was transported by the same merchant ship that brought the Nikopolis

⁴³ Unfortunately, the sarcophagus has not been thoroughly uncovered, so we do not know if there is a decoration on the sides of the chest.

sarcophagus, but in all probability the latter preceded by some years and was probably a trigger for the command of the former. Besides, Nikopolis was the metropolitan see of the province and would have had wealthier citizens than Alyzia.⁴⁴

Although the excavation in the cist tomb with the sarcophagus was never completed, a few bones were found, not in their original position.⁴⁵ On the contrary, the excavation of the monumental tomb in the north aisle was thorough, inside and out, but bones were not uncovered. This is of some importance, if we consider that the monumental tomb was erected in a very specific spot in the north aisle: the tomb containing the sarcophagus is right behind the north wall of the church (**fig. 1**). This relation between the sarcophagus tomb in the annex and the monumental tomb in the aisle does not seem unintended and needs to be interpreted.

Our first thoughts concern the relation between tombs and building. The substantial weight of the chest and lid of the marble sarcophagus suggests that it was placed in the specific tomb at the time when the walls of the annex (and of the church) began to be built around it. The monumental tomb in the aisle was erected only after the laying of the floor in the north aisle, since the

⁴⁴ For the ecclesiastical history of Epirus Vetus, cf. Chrysos 1981, pp. 79–80, 99–104; Dimitriadis 2001 (on Nikopolis); Bowden 2003, *passim*, spec. pp. 151–159.

⁴⁵ Vocotopoulos 1980, p. 35 says that the bones were found “disturbed”.

stylobate lies above the floor. The chancel and the canopy did not shape a fake tomb, since behind the screen there was a shallow pit grave that was covered by reused ancient blocs – one of them was uncovered in its original place (fig. 7). Thus, the sarcophagus was placed among the first and the monumental tomb was mounted among the last things in the church. Be that as it may, the sarcophagus would have been ordered and purchased during the last decades of the fifth century, if we accept a dating of the Nikopolis basilica Delta sometime after 474–475.⁴⁶ The construction of the Mytikas basilica is dated, consequently, to the last decades of the fifth century and the monumental tomb to the period around 500.

Our second consideration concerns the relation between tombs and people.⁴⁷ The cist and vaulted tombs of the northwest annex of the church were frequented by members of the Alyzian family who ordered and provided for the sarcophagus.⁴⁸ We can imagine the annex like a mausoleum in which several

⁴⁶ Varalis 2007, p. 596.

⁴⁷ We can only agree with one of the main conclusions of Yasin 2009, p. 239: "The church thus became an ideal site for the construction of commemorative monuments because it allowed those wishing to be remembered, both dead and the donors, to capitalize on a regular audience of gathered Christians whose predisposition toward commemoration and prayer was heightened with the incorporation of saints' cults within the space."

⁴⁸ Cf. above, note 22.

commemoration rites for the dead of this wealthy household could have taken place from time to time. The church was planned with this mausoleum, possibly because this was the only cemetery church in the region and because this was the only family that had the desire and the means to build such a mausoleum, if not the whole church.⁴⁹ The monumental tomb in the north aisle would have been easily perceived by anyone who entered the church from the west, as soon as they stood at the tribelon area or walked through the openings leading to the aisles. The colonnades were not blocked by parapets separating the nave from the aisles and obstructing the view to the tomb. This church was not destined for the celebration of the liturgy every day of the week or every Sunday; it served only funerals and other memorial rituals for the resident population,⁵⁰ and for this purpose it was not equipped with an ambo in the nave or an elaborate synthronon in the apse.⁵¹ The two large crosses that are shaped on the west part of the slate floor

⁴⁹ In Corinth, the capital of the Province of Achaia, where all the basilicas excavated are cemetery *extra muros* churches, apart from the pilgrimage basilica at Lechaion (St. Leonidis), the *mausolea* are numerous and the tombs plentiful. Cf. Rothaus 2000, pp. 93-104; Sanders 2005, pp. 437-441; Mailis 2011, pp. 88-93, nos. Ach.18-24.

⁵⁰ For such services, cf. Paxton 1990, 37-46.

⁵¹ The ambo is absent from the cemetery churches of Corinth; it is present though in the cathedral church of basilica Beta and absent at the basilica Delta of Nikopolis. Cf. Pallas 1977, pp. 153-171 and 134-137, respectively; Pallas 1979.

of the nave were feasibly destined to mark the specific spots where the funeral beds with the dead would be placed during the celebration of the funerals.⁵² Everyone attending and standing around these crosses on the floor could have get a glimpse of the monumental tomb in the north aisle and commemorate, apart from their own dead, this unfortunate woman who lived a pious life and loved her husband. This perpetual repetition of the commemoration of the 'privileged dead' was the purpose of the construction of this 'privileged tomb'. The veneration of the tomb, the lighting of the lamp that hanged above, the reading of the epigram inscribed on the slab, the prayer, the contemplation of any of the representations of the deceased, every single of these activities and all of them expressed the union of the living and the dead, the living on earth and the *living in God*. This recursive commemoration of the dead is also present in the liturgy.⁵³

One final question is left to be answered: what were the intentions of the family of Eunoia (or Eurynoa) and specifically of the beloved husband who dedicated the monumental tomb to his wife? The easy answer would be that the family decided to mount this tomb very close, almost adjacent, to a luxurious marble tomb of a saint. Hence the monumental tomb would be another burial

⁵² Cf. Vocotopoulos 1982, p. 91, pl. 64α-β.

⁵³ Cf. Yasin 2009, *passim*, spec. 212-222, where she comments on Augustine's *De cure pro mortuis gerenda*.

ad sanctum. We could also think of the sarcophagus as the tomb of the husband, who wished to be buried close to his wife for eternity. We could also imagine other scenarios, but methodologically it would be very precarious, for the sarcophagus is not yet excavated thoroughly and for the moment the available data are very thin. As the progress of our research is ongoing and the completion of the excavation is scheduled soon, we keep asking questions and we hope to find the right answers in the future.

Bibliography

1. Bandy A.C. (1970). *The Greek Christian Inscriptions of Crete*. Athens.
2. Bakirtzis Ch. (1997). *Αγίου Δημητρίου Θαύματα. Οι συλλογές αρχιεπισκόπου Ιωάννου και Ανωνύμου. Ο βίος, τα θαύματα και η Θεσσαλονίκη του Αγίου Δημητρίου*. Athens.
3. Bakirtzis Ch. (2002). Pilgrimage to Thessalonike: The Tomb of St. Demetrios. *DOP* 56, pp. 175-192.
4. Bowden W. (2003). *Epirus Vetus: The Archaeology of a Late Antique Province*. London.
5. Boziniis Ch. (2008). *Πλήρη θωράκια του Ελλαδικού χώρου από την παλαιοχριστιανική περίοδο έως το τέλος της Εικονομαχίας*, MA Thesis (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki).

6. Chalkia E. (1991). *Le mense paleocristiane. Tipologia e funzioni delle mense secondarie nel culto paleocristiano*. Città del Vaticano.
7. Chalkia E. (2004). Un sarcofago costantinopolitano a Nicopoli. *RACr* 80, pp. 211-231.
8. Chalkia E. (2007). Συμπληρωματική ανασκαφή στη βασιλική Δ της Νικόπολης: τα νέα ευρήματα. In: Zachos, pp. 659-666.
9. Chalkia E. (2015). *Η βασιλική Δ της Νικόπολης*. Athens.
10. Chrysos E. (1981). Συμβολή στην ιστορία της Ηπείρου κατά την πρωτοβυζαντινή περίοδο. *Epirotika Chronika* 23, pp. 9-111.
11. Cunliffe R.J. (2012). *A Lexicon of the Homeric Dialect, Expanded Edition*. Norman, Oklahoma.
12. Dagron G. (1978). *Vie et miracles de sainte Thècle*. Bruxelles.
13. De Vingo P., Marano Y.A., Pinar Gil J., eds. (2021). *Sepulture di prestigio nel bacino mediterraneo (secoli IV-IX). Definizione, immagini, utilizzo Atti del convegno, Pella (NO), 28-30 giugno 2017*, vols. 1-2. Sesto Fiorentino (FI).
14. Dimitriadis G.M. (2001). Nicopolis, la capitale paléochrétienne d'Épire, *Mésogeios* 12. pp. 13-36.

15. Duval Y. (1988) *Auprès des saints corps et âme: l'inhumation "ad sanctos" dans la chrétienté d'Orient et d'Occident du IIIe au VIIe siècle*. Paris.
16. Duval Y., Picard J.-C., eds. (1986). *L'inhumation privilégiée du IVe au VIIIe siècle en Occident, Actes du colloque tenu à Créteil les 16-18 mars 1984*. Paris.
17. Feissel D. (1983). *Recueil des inscriptions chrétiennes de Macédoine du IIIe au VIe siècle, BCH Suppl. VIII*. Athènes, Paris.
18. Feissel D., Philippidis- Braat A. (1985). Inventaires en vue d'un recueil des inscriptions historiques de Byzance, III. Inscriptions du Péloponnèse (à l'exception de Mistra), Première partie. Inscriptions du IVe au VIe siècle. *TravMem* 9, pp. 269-298, 358-374.
19. Gehrke H.-J., Wirbelauer E. (2004). Akarnania and Adjacent Areas. In: Hansen M.H., Nielsen Th.H. (eds.), *An Inventory of Archaic and Classical Poleis. An Investigation conducted by the Copenhagen Polis Centre for the Danish National Research Foundation*. Oxford, pp. 351-378.
20. Grabar A. (1946). *Martyrium. Recherches sur le culte des reliques et l'art chrétien antique, I. Architecture*. Paris (repr. London 1972).
21. Katopodis G. (2000). *Αρχαία Ακαρνανία*. Athens.

22. Kollwitz J., Herdejürgen H. (1979). *Die Sarkophage der Westlichen Gebiete des Imperium Romanum, II. Die Ravennatischen Sarkophage*. Berlin.
23. Koumoussi-Vyenoπούλου Α. (1996-1998). Ανασκαφικές «μαρτυρίες» του σεισμού του 552 μ.Χ. στην Πάτρα. *ΑΑΑ* 29-31, pp. 51-56.
24. Lazarides P. (1965). Βυζαντινά Αττικής και νήσων. *ADelt* 20, B, pp. 132-143.
25. Leriou A., Manolessou E.G. (2018). Βασιλική Κρανείου Αρχαίας Κορίνθου. Επανεξέταση δεδομένων του χώρου και του μνημείου. In: Zymi E., Karapanagiotou A.-V., Xanthopoulou M. eds. *Το Αρχαιολογικό Έργο στην Πελοπόννησο (ΑΕΠΕΛ1), Πρακτικά του Διεθνούς Συνεδρίου, Τρίπολη, 7-11 Νοεμβρίου 2012*. Kalamata, 761-770.
26. Liagos V. (2002). *Αλυζία: Ένας μικρός τόπος, μια μεγάλη ιστορία*. Agrinion.
27. Mauskopf Deliyannis D. (2017). *Ravenna in Late Antiquity*. Cambridge, New York, Melbourne, Delhi (repr.).
28. Mailis A. (2011). *The Annexes at the Early Christian Basilicas of Greece (4th – 6th c.), Architecture and Function*, BAR International Series 2312. Oxford.
29. Mentzos A. (1990). Η κοιμητηριακή ή έξω των τειχών βασιλική του Δίου. In: *AErgoMak* 4, pp. 231-240.

30. Mentzos A. (1994). *Το προσκύνημα του Αγίου Δημητρίου Θεσσαλονίκης στα βυζαντινά χρόνια*. Athens.
31. Moschos I., Portelanos A. (2010). *Alyzia: The Region of Kandela from Prehistory up to the End of Ancient Times. Technical and Defensive Works*. Kandela.
32. Moutsopoulos N.K. (1993-1996). Το παρεκκλήσι του Αγίου Ιωάννου του Προδρόμου στον Άγιο Δημήτριο Θεσσαλονίκης. *Βυζαντινά* 18, pp. 303-330 (repr. in: *idem, Βυζαντινά και οθωμανικά*. Thessaloniki 2005, pp. 136-153).
33. Moutsopoulos N.K. (1999). *Η βασιλική του Αγίου Αχιλλίου στην Πρέσπα, Ένα μνημείο κιβωτός της τοπικής ιστορίας*. Thessaloniki.
34. Murray W.M. (1982). *The Coastal Sites of Western Akarnania. A Topographical – Historical Survey*, PhD (University of Michigan, Ann Arbor).
35. Orlandos A. (1959). Ανασκαφή βασιλικής Δ Νικοπόλεως. *Prakt*, pp. 90-97.
36. Pallas D. (1971). In: *^LRBK II*, col. 207-334, s.v. Epirus.
37. Pallas D. (1977). *Les monuments paléochrétiens de Grèce découverts de 1959 à 1973, Sussidi allo studio delle antichità cristiane V*. Città del Vaticano.
38. Pallas D. (1979). Corinthe et Nikopolis pendant le bas moyen-âge. *FelRav* 118, pp. 93-142.

39. Pantermalis D. (1999). *Δίον. Η ανακάλυψη*. Athens.
40. Pantazides J. (1892). *Λεξικόν Ομηρικόν περιέχον πάσας τας παρ' Ομήρω και τοις ομηρίδαις ευρισκομένας λέξεις*. Αθήναι.
41. Papadopoulou V. (2013). *Παλαιοχριστιανική Ήπειρος (4ος- 7ος): Η μαρτυρία της γλυπτικής*, PhD (University of Ioannina, Ioannina).
42. Papaggeli P. (1984). Ομάδα σαρκοφάγων στη Νικόπολη. *Epirotika Chronika* 26, pp. 43-70.
43. Paxton F.S. (1990). *Christianizing Death. The Creation of a Ritual Process in Early Medieval Europe*. London.
44. Paxton F.S. (2005). Communities of the Living and the Dead in Late Antiquity, and the Early Medieval West. In: Williams M. ed. *The Making of Christian Communities in Late Antiquity and the Middle Ages*. London, pp. 49-62.
45. Pelekanides S. (1955). Η έξω των τειχών παλαιοχριστιανική βασιλική των Φιλίππων. *AEphem*, pp. 114-179.
46. Pilhofer P. (2009). *Philippi, II. Katalog der Inschriften von Philippi*. Tübingen, 2nd ed.
47. Rebillard É. (2003). *Religion et sépulture. L'Église, les vivants et les morts dans l'Antiquité tardive*. Paris.
48. Rizakis A.D. (2008). *Achaïe III. Les cités achéennes: épigraphie et histoire, Meletēmata* 55. Athens.

49. Rothaus R.M. (2000). *Corinth: The First City of Greece. An Urban History of Late Antique Cult and Religion*. Leiden, Boston, Köln.
50. Sanders G.D.R. (2005). Archaeological Evidence for Early Christianity and the End of Hellenic Religion in Corinth. In: Schowalter D.N., Friesen S.J. eds. *Urban Religion in Roman Corinth. Interdisciplinary Approaches*. Cambridge, Massachusetts, pp. 419-442.
51. Sodini J.-P. (1986). Les 'tombes privilégiées' dans l'Orient chrétien (à l'exception du diocèse d'Egypte). In: Duval, Picard, pp. 233-243.
52. Sodini J.-P., Kolokotsas K. (1984). *Aliki II, La basilique double, Études thasiennes X*. Athènes, Paris.
53. Soteriou G.A. (1929). Αι παλαιοχριστιανικά βασιλικά της Ελλάδος. *AEphem*, pp. 161-248.
54. Soteriou M. and G.A. (1952). *Η βασιλική του Αγίου Δημητρίου Θεσσαλονίκης*. Athens.
55. Soustal P., Koder J. (1981). *Nikopolis und Kephalaria, Tabula Imperii Byzantini 3*. Wien.
56. Varalis I.D. (2007). Τα χαρακτηριστικά της εκκλησιαστικής αρχιτεκτονικής της Νικόπολης: Παραλληλίες και διαφοροποιήσεις. In: Zachos, pp. 595-607.

57. Vocotopoulos P.L. (1968). Μεσαιωνικά μνημεία του Μύτικα Ακαρνανίας. *AAA* 1, 152-154.
58. Vocotopoulos P.L. (1972). *Prakt*, pp. 109-113.
59. Vocotopoulos P.L. (1979). *Prakt*, pp. 121-126.
60. Vocotopoulos P.L. (1980). *Prakt*, pp. 34-36.
61. Vocotopoulos P.L. (1981). *Prakt*, pp. 79-81.
62. Vocotopoulos P.L. (1982). *Prakt*, pp. 91-94.
63. Vocotopoulos P.L. (1983). *Prakt*, pp. 84-86.
64. Vocotopoulos P.L. (1984). *Prakt*, pp. 129-130.
65. Yasin A.M. (2005). Funerary Monuments and Collective Identity: From Roman Family to Christian Community. *ArtB* 87/3, pp. 433-457.
66. Yasin A.M. (2009). *Saints and Church Spaces in the Late Antique Mediterranean. Architecture, Cult, and Community*. Cambridge, New York.
67. Zachos K., ed. (2007). *Νικόπολις Β': Πρακτικά του Δευτέρου Διεθνούς Συμποσίου για τη Νικόπολη (11-15 Σεπτεμβρίου 2002)*. Preveza.
68. Zachos K. (2015). *Αρχαιολογικός οδηγός Νικόπολης. Περιδιάβαση στο ιστορικό, ιερό και αστικό τοπίο*. Athens.

ISSN 2732-8260